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The Employment Rate in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022

It grew by an average of 3.10% between 2018 and 2022

Istat calculates the employment rate in Italian regions and macro-regions. The employment rate is defined as the percentage of employed people aged 20-64 in the population aged 20-64. The data analyzed refers to the period between 2018 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by employment rate in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place in terms of employment rate with a value of 77.1 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with a value of 74.9 units and from Emilia Romagna with a value of 74.8 units. In the middle of the table we find Piedmont with a value of 71.3 units, followed by Liguria with a value of 70.7 and Umbria with a value of 47.3 units. Campania closes the ranking with a value of 47.3 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 47 and Sicily with a value of 46.2 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the employment rate between 2018 and 2022. Puglia is in first place for percentage growth in the employment rate between 2018 and 2022 with a change of an amount of 49.40 units up to a value of 53.40 units or equal to a value of 8.10%. Basilicata follows with a change in the employment rate between 2018 and 2022 from an amount of 53.30 units up to a value of 57.30 or equal to an amount of 4 units equal to 7.50%. Finally, in third place Liguria with a change in the employment rate from an amount of 67.40 units up to a value of 70.70 units equal to a value of 3.30 units equivalent to 4.90%. In the middle of the table is Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation from an amount of 70.90 units up to a value of 73.40 units equal to a variation of 2.50 units equivalent to a value of 3.53%. Tuscany follows with a variation from an amount of 71.30 units up to a value of 73.70 units or equivalent to a value of 2.40 units equal to an amount of 3.37%. Calabria closes the mid-table group with a variation from an amount of 45.50 units up to a value of 47.00 units or equal to an amount of 1.50 units equivalent to an amount of 3.30%. Piedmont closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 70.70 units up to 71.30 units or equal to a value of 0.60 units equivalent to a value of +0.85%. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a value of the employment rate growing from an amount of 765.50 units up to a value of 77.10 units or equal to an amount of 0.60 units equivalent to a value of 0.78%. . Finally, Emilia Romagna closes where the employment rate grew between 2018 and 2022 from an amount of 74.40 units up to a value of 74.80 units or equal to a value of 0.40 units equivalent to a value by 0.54%. On average the value of the employment rate grew from an amount of 63.14 units up to a value of 65.1 units or equal to a variation of 1.96 units equivalent to a growth of 3.10%.

Ranking of Italian macro-regions by percentage change in the employment rate value. The South is in first place in terms of the percentage change in the value of the employment rate, going from an amount of 48.6 units in 2018 to a value of 51.1 units in 2022, or a change equal to 2.5 units equivalent to a value of 5.14%. In second place is the South with a variation from 48.2 in 2018 up to 50.5 in 2022 or equal to a +2.3 units equivalent to a value of +4.77%. In third place are the Islands where the employment rate between 2018 and 2022 went from an amount of 47.2 units up to a value of 49.3

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units or equal to a variation of 2.1 units equivalent to a variation of 4.45%. The Center is in fourth place with a variation from an amount of 67.7 units up to a value of 69.7 units or equal to a variation of 2 units equivalent to a value of 2.95%. The North-East follows with a variation from an amount of 73 units up to a value of 74.1 units or equal to a variation of 1.1 units equivalent to a variation of 1.51%. The North-West is in sixth place with a variation from an amount of 71.6 units up to a value of 72.6 units or equal to a variation of 1 unit equivalent to a value of 1.4%. The North closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 72.2 units up to a value of 73.2 units or equal to a value of 1 unit equivalent to a value of 1.39%.

Changes in the employment rate pre- and post-Covid 19. Below we analyze the impact of Covid 19 on the trend in the employment rate in the Italian regions. To consider this trend we will analyze three variables, namely the pre-Covid 19 average, or the average of the employment rate between 2018 and 2019, the 2020 value considered as the Covid 19 value, and the value of the post Covid19 average considered as the 2021 average. -2021. In general we can note that all the regions have reduced the employment rate in the comparison between the pre-Covid 19 average and the Covid 19. Just as the value of the employment rate has grown in all the Italian regions between the Covid 19 and the Post -COVID-19. In particular, considering the average value for all Italian regions we can notice a reduction in the value of the employment rate between the pre-Covid 19 average and Covid 19 with a value of -1.98%. However, following Covid 19, the employment rate began to grow positively with an average value of +3.05%. Overall, on average, between pre-Covid 19 and post-Covid 19 the value of the employment rate grew by 0.64%. However, if we analyze the individual regions we can notice that not all regions reacted positively in a comparison between pre-Covid 19 and post-Covid 19. In this regard, it is possible to establish a ranking of the Italian regions on the basis of the following indicator: $\text{AveragePostCovid} / \text{AveragePreCovid} * 100$. We can note that there are regions that can be considered as "winning" or that have seen the value of the employment rate increase in the comparison between pre-Covid19 and post-Covid19, and "losing" regions or regions for which the employment rate between pre-Covid19 and post-Covid19 has decreased.

Winning regions. The winning regions are those regions in which the employment rate, despite having had a negative decline between pre-Covid19 and post-Covid19, have recorded positive values in terms of employment rate between pre-Covid19 and post-Covid19. COVID-19. The employment rate in Basilicata grew by a value of 5.56% in comparison between the pre-Covid19 average and the post-Covid19 average. Positive variations in the pre-Covid19 average and the post-Covid19 average were also recorded in Puglia with a value of +4.32%, Liguria with +2.74%, Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 2.46% , Campania with +2.21%, Sardinia with +2.12%, Umbria with +1.98%, Sicily with +1.91%, Calabria with +1.87%, Marche with +1.51%, Tuscany with +0.84%, Valle d'Aosta with +0.41%, Abruzzo with +0.32%.

Losing regions. Among the regions for which there was a reduction in the employment rate between the pre-Covid19 average and the post-Covid19 average, i.e. losing regions, there are Piedmont with -0.28%, Veneto with -0.35 %, Lombardy with -0.68%, Emilia Romagna with -1.00%, Molise with -1.12%, Trentino Alto Adige with -1.24%. If we compare the losing regions with the winning regions we can notice that many winning regions are southern while many losing regions are northern. This result may appear paradoxical. However, it could be explained by considering that regions that have low employment rates, as in the case of the South, are more likely to grow in the employment rate compared to the Northern regions which instead have very high employment rates.

Clustering using the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering using the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Veneto, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Marche, Emilia Romagna, Umbria, Trentino Alto Adige, Liguria, Lazio, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Calabria, Campania, Sicily, Puglia, Basilicata, Sardinia, Molise.

We can see that the average value of the employment rate of the regions of cluster 1 is higher than the value of the employment rate of cluster 2. The regions of Cluster 1 are regions of Northern Italy with the sole exception of Abruzzo. While the regions of Cluster 2 are southern regions. We can note that there is therefore a significant difference between the regions of Central-Northern Italy and the regions of Southern Italy.

Conclusions. We can see that the employment rate grew in the period considered, i.e. between 2018 and 2022 in all regions. On average between 2018 and 2022 the employment rate grew by an amount equal to 3.10%. We can therefore summarize the major propositions suggested by the data analysis:

- There is a significant difference in terms of employment rate between the South and the Centre-North detected in the period between 2018 and 2022;
- The employment rate in the South grew faster than in the Central-Northern regions between 2018 and 2022;
- All Italian regions reduced the employment rate in the transition between the pre-Covid19 period and the Covid19 period;
- All Italian regions saw the employment rate grow in the transition between Covid and the post-Covid19 average;
- However, some regions in the post-Covid19 period have not yet reached the level of the pre-Covid19 employment rate and these regions are: Piedmont, Veneto, Lombardy, Emilia Romagna, Molise, Trentino Alto Adige.

Finally we can note that in the current job market, and especially in the current macro-economic context consisting of inflation and international uncertainties, it is not sufficient to calculate the number of people who work and who are employed. In fact, the problem of the working poor is becoming increasingly serious: people who, despite working, remain poor or subject to financial fragility. It follows that it would also be necessary to calculate how many people are employed and who also risk poverty. We could thus discover that many workers in Northern Italy, who live in the metropolitan areas of the large productive cities of the North, experience new forms of poverty even though they appear formally employed in the official Istat statistics. Finally we must consider that the real employment rate in the southern regions could be higher than that officially recorded due to the presence of illegal work. It follows that labor markets are largely inefficient and incapable both of guaranteeing adequate wages for workers and of bringing workers out of the underground, informal and illegal economy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Leogrande, D., & Anobile, F. (2023). Beds in Health Facilities in the Italian Regions: A Socio-Economic Approach. Available at SSRN 4577029.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, D. (2023). The Socio-Economic Determinants of the Number of Physicians in Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4560149.

Leogrande, A., Leogrande, D., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of Unemployment in the ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4502940.

Leogrande, A., Leogrande, D., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Patent Applications in the Context of the ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4514191.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Government Expenditure on Education in the ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4438106.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Determinants of Emissions in the Context of ESG Models at World Level.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4388957.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Leogrande, A., Leogrande, D., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Patent Applications in the Context of the ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4514191.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Fight Against Corruption at Global Level. A Metric Approach. A Metric Approach (December 30, 2022).

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis. A Data-Driven Analysis (December 25, 2022).

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). k-Means Clusterization and Machine Learning Prediction of European Most Cited Scientific Publications. Available at SSRN 4195846.

Appendix

Tasso di Occupazione					
Regione	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
<i>Piemonte</i>	70,7	70,8	68,7	69,8	71,3
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	72,6	73,3	71,6	71,6	74,9
<i>Liguria</i>	67,4	67,6	65,8	68	70,7
<i>Lombardia</i>	72,6	73,4	71,1	71,6	73,4
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	76,5	76,7	74,4	74,2	77,1
<i>Veneto</i>	71,5	72,7	70,2	70,8	72,9
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	70,9	71,3	71,4	72,3	73,4
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	74,4	75,4	73,2	73,5	74,8
<i>Toscana</i>	71,3	71,7	70,2	70,5	73,7
<i>Umbria</i>	67,4	69,1	67,7	69,3	69,9
<i>Marche</i>	69,1	69,7	68,2	68,9	72
<i>Lazio</i>	65,3	65,6	63,8	64,4	66,5
<i>Abruzzo</i>	62,1	62,4	60,7	62,1	62,8
<i>Molise</i>	57,3	58,7	56,8	55,9	58,8
<i>Campania</i>	45,2	45,1	43,8	45	47,3
<i>Puglia</i>	49,4	50,2	49,4	50,5	53,4
<i>Basilicata</i>	53,3	54,7	54	56,7	57,3
<i>Calabria</i>	45,5	45,3	44	45,5	47
<i>Sicilia</i>	44,3	44,7	43,9	44,5	46,2
<i>Sardegna</i>	56	57,2	55,2	57	58,6

Regione	Media Pre covid			Pre Covid sui Covid		Post Covid su Covid		Post Covid su Pre Covid	
	Pre covid	Covid	Post Covid	Var Ass	Var Per	Var Ass	Var Per	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	70,75	68,7	70,55	-2,05	-2,90	1,85	2,69	-0,20	-0,28
Valle d'Aosta	72,95	71,6	73,25	-1,35	-1,85	1,65	2,30	0,30	0,41
Liguria	67,5	65,8	69,35	-1,70	-2,52	3,55	5,40	1,85	2,74
Lombardia	73	71,1	72,5	-1,90	-2,60	1,40	1,97	-0,50	-0,68
Trentino-Alto Adige	76,6	74,4	75,65	-2,20	-2,87	1,25	1,68	-0,95	-1,24
Veneto	72,1	70,2	71,85	-1,90	-2,64	1,65	2,35	-0,25	-0,35
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	71,1	71,4	72,85	0,30	0,42	1,45	2,03	1,75	2,46
Emilia-Romagna	74,9	73,2	74,15	-1,70	-2,27	0,95	1,30	-0,75	-1,00
Toscana	71,5	70,2	72,1	-1,30	-1,82	1,90	2,71	0,60	0,84
Umbria	68,25	67,7	69,6	-0,55	-0,81	1,90	2,81	1,35	1,98
Marche	69,4	68,2	70,45	-1,20	-1,73	2,25	3,30	1,05	1,51
Lazio	65,45	63,8	65,45	-1,65	-2,52	1,65	2,59	0,00	0,00
Abruzzo	62,25	60,7	62,45	-1,55	-2,49	1,75	2,88	0,20	0,32
Molise	58	56,8	57,35	-1,20	-2,07	0,55	0,97	-0,65	-1,12
Campania	45,15	43,8	46,15	-1,35	-2,99	2,35	5,37	1,00	2,21
Puglia	49,8	49,4	51,95	-0,40	-0,80	2,55	5,16	2,15	4,32
Basilicata	54	54	57	0,00	0,00	3,00	5,56	3,00	5,56
Calabria	45,4	44	46,25	-1,40	-3,08	2,25	5,11	0,85	1,87
Sicilia	44,5	43,9	45,35	-0,60	-1,35	1,45	3,30	0,85	1,91
Sardegna	56,6	55,2	57,8	-1,40	-2,47	2,60	4,71	1,20	2,12
Media	63,46	62,21	64,1025	-1,25	-1,98	1,90	3,05	0,64	

Tasso di Occupazione nelle Macro-Regioni

Macro-Regioni	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord	72,2	72,9	70,8	71,4	73,2	1,00	1,39
Nord-ovest	71,6	72,1	70	70,8	72,6	1,00	1,40
Nord-est	73	73,9	71,8	72,3	74,1	1,10	1,51
Centro	67,7	68,2	66,6	67,2	69,7	2,00	2,95
Mezzogiorno	48,2	48,5	47,4	48,5	50,5	2,30	4,77
Sud	48,6	48,9	47,7	48,9	51,1	2,50	5,14
Isole	47,2	47,8	46,7	47,7	49,3	2,10	4,45

**Ranking delle Regioni per Valore della Variazione
dell'Occupazione tra il 2018 ed il 2022.**

Rank	Regione	2018	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Puglia</i>	49,40	53,40	4,00	8,10
2	<i>Basilicata</i>	53,30	57,30	4,00	7,50
3	<i>Liguria</i>	67,40	70,70	3,30	4,90
4	<i>Campania</i>	45,20	47,30	2,10	4,65
5	<i>Sardegna</i>	56,00	58,60	2,60	4,64
6	<i>Sicilia</i>	44,30	46,20	1,90	4,29
7	<i>Marche</i>	69,10	72,00	2,90	4,20
8	<i>Umbria</i>	67,40	69,90	2,50	3,71
9	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	70,90	73,40	2,50	3,53
10	<i>Toscana</i>	71,30	73,70	2,40	3,37
11	<i>Calabria</i>	45,50	47,00	1,50	3,30
12	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	72,60	74,90	2,30	3,17
13	<i>Molise</i>	57,30	58,80	1,50	2,62
14	<i>Veneto</i>	71,50	72,90	1,40	1,96
15	<i>Lazio</i>	65,30	66,50	1,20	1,84
16	<i>Abruzzo</i>	62,10	62,80	0,70	1,13
17	<i>Lombardia</i>	72,60	73,40	0,80	1,10
18	<i>Piemonte</i>	70,70	71,30	0,60	0,85
19	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	76,50	77,10	0,60	0,78
20	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	74,40	74,80	0,40	0,54
	<i>Media</i>	63,1	65,1	1,96	3,10

